

Supplementary Information (SI)

Visualization of latent fingerprints by combined tetra-*n*-butylammonium iodide dusting and nitrogen dioxide treatment: Mechanistic insights

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S1. Experimental section

S1.1 Reagents

Tetra-*n*-butylammonium hydroxide triacontahydrate ((C₄H₉)₄NOH·30H₂O, abbreviated as TBAOH·30H₂O, analytical grade purity, Sigma-Aldrich); Hydroiodic acid (HI, 57 wt.% aqueous solution stabilized with 1.5 wt.% H₃PO₂, analytical grade purity, Carlo Erba, Milano); Tetra-*n*-butylammonium iodide powder ((C₄H₉)₄NI, abbreviated as TBAI, synthesized from tetra-*n*-butylammonium hydroxide and hydroiodic acid, then purified by recrystallization, as described in subsection S1.2); Iodine (I₂, analytical grade purity, Kemika, Zagreb); Zinc pellets (Zn, analytical grade purity, Merck, Darmstadt); Nitric acid (HNO₃, 69 wt.%, aqueous solution, trace purity, Merck, Darmstadt); NO₂ (the gas is generated via reaction between Zn and HNO₃, according to the method adopted from Stojkovikj et. al.^[1]); Methanol (CH₃OH, analytical grade purity, Alkaloid, Skopje); Refined sunflower cooking oil (obtained from a local producer); *Tert*-butanol (2-methylpropan-2-ol, (CH₃)₃COH, analytical grade purity, Sigma-Aldrich Chemie); Potassium bromide (KBr, FTIR spectroscopy grade purity); Fully deuterated dimethyl sulfoxide (CD₃)₂SO or DMSO-D₆, NMR spectroscopy grade purity) and Deionized water.

S1.2 Synthesis of tetra-*n*-butylammonium iodide - TBAI powder and visualization of the latent fingerprints via TBAI dusting and NO₂ treatment

A mass of 30 g of TBAOH·30H₂O was introduced into a 250 mL beaker positioned on an electromagnetic stirrer/heating plate (model Stuart). In a next step, 20 mL of 57 wt.% HI(aq) are added slowly, 1 mL-by-1 mL, and in case of undissolved substance, 20-50 mL of deionized water are added to the beaker after which the solution is left to stir for around 30 minutes. A neutralization reaction takes place, as described with **Equation S1**, where the as-synthesized tetra-*n*-butylammonium iodide – (C₄H₉)₄NI is abbreviated as TBAI for simplicity. The excess water is evaporated by heating the solution to 80 °C and after cooling to room temperature, the beaker is placed in a refrigerator (~5 °C) and left overnight. The TBAI crystals that formed from the cold solution are separated via vacuum filtration and rinsed with cold deionized water. The TBAI is purified via recrystallization by dissolving the substance

in 250 mL deionized water. The solution is heated at 80 °C for 15 minutes and again after cooling to room temperature, is placed in a refrigerator and left overnight. The TBAI crystals are again separated from the aqueous phase via vacuum filtration using Büchner funnel and blue-ribbon filter paper, rinsed with cold deionized water and left to dry under ambient conditions. After drying the TBAI is grounded in fine powder using pestle and mortar.

Equation S1

The TBAI was used for dusting the latent forefinger fingerprints impressed on various porous (standard 80 gsm paper) and non-porous (laminated chipboard, glass and glazed ceramics) surfaces prior to their visualization via treatment with nitrogen dioxide (NO₂) gas. The procedures for TBAI dusting and NO₂ gas generation/samples treatment are described in Singh et al.^[2] and Stojkovicj et al.,^[1] respectively.

S1.3 Deposition and visualization of latent fingerprints

Latent fingerprints of sebaceous nature are deposited (impressed) on various non-porous: laminated wooden chipboard, glass and glazed ceramics, and porous surfaces: 80 g·m⁻² (gsm) standard office printing paper, by two donors.

The process of fingerprints preparation included washing the hands thoroughly with water and soap, rubbing the right-hand forefinger around the nose and depositing each fingerprint on the surface of each sample under an applied pressure corresponding to a mass load in the range of 400–700 g, as measured on a balance^[1]. The samples with deposited latent fingerprints are dusted with fine powdered TBAI which adheres to the surface of the sebaceous residue. In a next step, the samples are placed in a vessel (closed chamber) with nitrogen dioxide (NO₂) gas, generated via reaction between zinc pellets and aqueous solution of diluted nitric acid (HNO₃), as described in our previous research^[1]. The NO₂ gas treatment time was varied depending on the intended experimental purpose. The NO₂ exposure of the samples used for forensic evaluation of the TBAI/NO₂ method was 5 seconds, while for the purpose of spectroscopic characterization, longer NO₂ exposure times were also used for threatening the latent fingerprints and other samples included in various experiments (as described in Table S1-Table S5).

The visualized fingerprints on various porous and non-porous surfaces are presented in Figure 1. As a control experiment, latent fingerings impressed on various surfaces were exposed to NO₂ gas from 5 seconds up to 10 minutes, without TBAI pre-treatment, thus no visualization occurred (Figure S6).

S1.4 Characterization methods

The visualized fingerprints impressed on various porous and non-porous surfaces were photographed and processed for forensic examination of the first (pattern type and ridge clarity), second (minutiae quantification) and third level (pore observation) characteristics.

The characterization methods used for revealing the fingerprints visualization mechanism involved Raman, Fourier Transform Infrared (FTIR), Ultraviolet-Visible (UV-Vis) and Proton Nuclear Magnetic Resonance (¹H-NMR) spectroscopy.

The Raman spectra are recorded using the Horiba Jobin Yvon LabRAM 300 system with the following parameters: Red laser beam ($\lambda = 632.8$ nm) without beam intensity attenuation filter; Range – 50 to 3200 cm⁻¹; Exposure time – 15; Resistance temperature detector exposure time – 1 and Accumulation number – 10. The samples subjected to examination with Raman spectroscopy are described in **Table S1**.

The UV-Vis analysis is performed on samples dissolved in organic solvent (methanol or *tert*-butanol). For this purpose, Varian Cary 50 Scan UV-Vis spectrometer is used, with the following spectra acquisition parameters: Wavelength range – 800 to 200 nm; Recording rate – Medium and Baseline correction (blank sample) – pristine solvent (methanol or *tert*-butanol). The samples and their

preparation in methanol and *tert*-butanol as solvents are described in **Table S2** and **Table S3**, respectively.

The FTIR spectra of oil-based samples and NO₂ treated TBAI (Samples 1, 2, 2*, 3, 4, 4* and 5 - preparation described in **Table S4**) are recorded by placing one drop of each sample between two KBr tablets prepared via pressing 250 mg pre-dried KBr (at 120 °C) in a hydraulic press by applying pressure of 10,000 kg·cm⁻². On the other hand, the spectrum of powder TBAI (Sample 6 in **Table S4**) is recorded on a tablet prepared via mixing 2 mg TBAI with 250 mg pre-dried KBr, while the spectrum of human sebum (Sample 0) is recorded after impressing sebaceous latent fingerprint on the surface of 250 mg KBr tablet. The background spectrum for all FTIR spectra is recorded using blank (pristine) KBr tablet, prepared in the same manner, as described above in this paragraph. The FTIR characterization parameters and instrument configuration used in this research, are the following: Perkin Elmer FTIR 2000 system (spectra recording parameters: Wavenumber range – 4000 to 400 cm⁻¹; Resolution – 2 cm⁻¹; Interval – 0.5 cm⁻¹ and Number of scans – 32).

Bruker Avance Neo 500 MHz NMR spectrometer is utilized for recording ¹H NMR spectra in an extended (0 to 11 ppm) and shorter chemical shift ranges. Fully deuterated dimethyl sulfoxide – (CD₃)₂SO or DMSO-D₆ is used as solvent, and the samples preparation and description are presented in **Table S5**. 0.5 mL of each liquid sample, or the solid TBAI (pre-dried) in case of Sample 6 (see **Table S5**), are transferred into standard 5 mm NMR tubes. All spectra are acquired at 298 K under standard acquisition parameters for ¹H NMR.

The Raman, FTIR and UV-Vis spectroscopy characterization data is processed with the OriginPro software and exported as graphs.

The y-axis intensity and transmittance values in the Raman and FTIR spectroscopy, respectively are normalized between 0 and 1, according to **Equation S2**:

$$NV = (MV - \text{Min}V) / (\text{Max}V - \text{Min}V) \quad \text{Equation S2}$$

Where:

NV – Normalized values of intensity or transmittance.

MV – Measured values of intensity or transmittance.

MinV – Minimal measured values of intensity or transmittance.

MaxV – Maximal measured values of intensity or transmittance.

Table S1. Preparation of samples for characterization with Raman spectroscopy.

Sample	Description of sample preparation	Color of the visualized fingerprint
Freshly impressed fingerprint residue (Human sebum – Sample 0)	A forefinger fingerprint is impressed on glass surface after rubbing the finger near the nose sides to collect sebaceous secret. This sample is chemically equivalent to Sample 0 characterized with FTIR, as described in Table S2 in SI .	Latent fingerprint – not visible
Fingerprint on glass (5 s NO ₂)	A forefinger fingerprint is impressed on glass surface after rubbing the finger near the nose sides to collect sebaceous secret. The sample is exposed to NO ₂ gas for 5 seconds in a 750 mL container.	Dark yellow
Fingerprint on paper (5 s NO ₂)	A forefinger fingerprint is impressed on 80 gsm paper surface after rubbing the finger near the nose sides to collect sebaceous secret. The sample is exposed to NO ₂ gas for 5 seconds in a 750 mL container.	Dark yellow
Fingerprint on paper (20 s NO ₂)	A forefinger fingerprint is impressed on 80 gsm paper surface after rubbing the finger near the nose sides to collect sebaceous secret. The sample is exposed to NO ₂ gas for 20 seconds in a 750 mL container.	Orange
Fingerprint on paper – visualized 2 months ago	A forefinger fingerprint is impressed on 80 gsm paper surface after rubbing the finger near the nose sides to collect sebaceous secret. The sample was exposed to NO ₂ gas for 20 seconds in a 750 mL container and left under ambient conditions for 2 months.	Dark brown

Sample	Description of sample preparation	Color of the visualized fingerprint
(20 s NO₂)		
TBAI + NO₂ (5 s)	50 mg TBAI is placed in vial and exposed to NO ₂ gas for 5 seconds in a 750 mL container.	Not applicable
Pristine TBAI	Pure dry TBAI, synthesized as-described in Subsection S1.2 in SI .	Not applicable

Table S2. Preparation of samples for characterization with UV-Vis spectroscopy in methanol (MeOH) as solvent.

Sample	Description of sample preparation
81 $\mu\text{mol}\cdot\text{dm}^{-3}$ TBAI_(MeOH)	15 mg TBAI are dissolved in 50 mL methanol, then diluted 10 times with additional methanol.
131 $\mu\text{mol}\cdot\text{dm}^{-3}$ I₂(MeOH)	15 mg iodine crystals are dissolved in 150 mL methanol, then diluted 3 times with additional methanol.
TBAI(s) exposed to NO₂(g), then dissolved in MeOH	15 mg TBAI are exposed to NO ₂ gas filled into a container with volume of 750 mL for 5 minutes, then the solid product is dissolved in 50 mL methanol and diluted 4 times with additional methanol.

Table S3. Preparation of samples for characterization with UV-Vis spectroscopy in *tert*-butanol (*t*-BuOH) as solvent.

Sample	Description of sample preparation
135.5 $\mu\text{mol}\cdot\text{dm}^{-3}$ TBAI_(t-BuOH)	10 mg TBAI are dissolved with in 10 mL <i>tert</i> -butanol, then diluted 20 times with additional <i>tert</i> -butanol.
68 $\mu\text{mol}\cdot\text{dm}^{-3}$ TBAI_(t-BuOH)	10 mg TBAI are dissolved with in 10 mL <i>tert</i> -butanol, then diluted 40 times with additional <i>tert</i> -butanol.
34 $\mu\text{mol}\cdot\text{dm}^{-3}$ TBAI_(t-BuOH)	10 mg TBAI are dissolved with in 10 mL <i>tert</i> -butanol, then diluted 80 times with additional <i>tert</i> -butanol.
TBAI(s) exposed to NO₂(g), then dissolved in t-BuOH	50 mg TBAI are exposed to NO ₂ gas filled into a container with volume of 750 mL for 5 minutes, then the solid product is dissolved in 10 mL <i>tert</i> -butanol and diluted 50 times with additional <i>tert</i> -butanol.

Table S4. Preparation of samples for characterization with FTIR spectroscopy.

Sample No.	Description of sample preparation and sample annotations
Sample 0 (S0)	Sebaceous fingerprint residue – prepared by forefinger on the sides of the nose and impressing the collected sebaceous secretion on a surface of KBr tablet (Sebum).
Sample 1 (S1)	Sunflower oil without any additives (Pristine sunflower oil).
Sample 2 (S2)	50 mg TBAI mixed with 7 mL sunflower oil, sonicated for 15 min prior to recording FTIR spectrum (Oil + TBAI_{dil.}).
Sample 2* (S2*)	250 mg TBAI mixed with 0.5 mL sunflower oil, sonicated for 15 min prior to recording FTIR spectrum (Oil + TBAI_{conc.}).
Sample 3 (S3)	3 mL sunflower oil exposed to 7 mL NO ₂ gas in a syringe and mixed. This procedure is repeated 10 times, and the sample is sonicated for 15 min prior to recording FTIR spectrum (Oil + NO₂).
Sample 4 (S4)	50 mg TBAI is added in 7 mL sunflower oil, then exposed to 7 mL NO ₂ gas in a syringe and mixed. This procedure is repeated 10 times, and the sample is sonicated for 15 min prior to recording FTIR spectrum (Oil + TBAI_{dil.} + NO₂).

Sample No.	Description of sample preparation and sample annotations
Sample 4* (S4*)	250 mg TBAI is added in 0.5 mL sunflower oil, then exposed to NO ₂ gas for 5 minutes in a 750 mL jar. The sample is sonicated for 15 min prior to recording FTIR spectrum (Oil + TBAI _{conc.} + NO ₂).
Sample 5 (S5)	Pure dry TBAI, synthesized as-described in Subsection S1.2 in SI (TBAI) .
Sample 6 (S6)	50 mg TBAI is placed in vial and exposed to NO ₂ gas for 5 min in a 750 mL container (TBAI + NO ₂).

Table S5. Preparation of samples for characterization with ¹H NMR spectroscopy.

Sample No.	Description of sample preparation
Sample 1	Pristine sunflower oil.
Sample 2	50 mg TBAI mixed with 7 mL sunflower oil, sonicated for uniform solution.
Sample 3	3 mL sunflower oil is exposed to 70 mL NO ₂ gas (3 mL oil is placed in a syringe, then 7 mL NO ₂ is withdrawn, the content in the syringe is shaken and sonicated – this procedure is repeated 10 times with fresh NO ₂).
Sample 4	50 mg TBAI is mixed with 7 mL sunflower oil and sonicated. 3 mL of the TBAI in sunflower oil sample is exposed to 70 mL NO ₂ gas (3 mL oil is placed in a syringe, then 7 mL NO ₂ is withdrawn, the content in the syringe is shaken and sonicated – this procedure is repeated 10 times with fresh NO ₂).
Sample 5	Pristine TBAI powder as a reference material (dried prior to characterization).
Sample 6	50 mg TBAI is placed in vial and exposed to NO ₂ gas for 5 minutes in a 750 mL container.

S2. Results

S2.1 Supporting figures

Figure S1. Full range Raman spectra of visualized fingerprints on glass and paper surfaces under various conditions and Raman spectra of pristine TBAI and TBAI treated with NO₂ gas.

Figure S2. UV-Vis spectra of TBAI with various concentrations and TBAI exposed to NO₂ in *tert*-butanol as solvent.

Figure S3. TBAI dissolved in *tert*-butanol, kept under sunlight and under dark conditions and TBAI dissolved in methanol, kept only under sunlight.

Figure S4. Raman spectrum of freshly impressed fingerprint on glass slide surface. No distinctive Raman signal is observed.

Figure S5. Sebaceous fingerprints impressed on 80 gsm paper and visualized with the TBAI/NO₂ method by varying the NO₂ treatment duration.

Figure S6. Control experiment: Sebaceous fingerprints impressed on 80 gsm paper and treated with NO₂ for 5 seconds, 20 seconds, 1 minute and 10 minutes, without TBAI pre-treatment. No visualization of the latent fingerprints occurred. The paper's surface turns orange-brownish after longer NO₂ exposure (20 seconds, 1 minute and 10 minutes), most possibly due to nitration reactions involving paper additives.

Figure S7a. ^1H NMR spectrum of **Sample 1 (Pristine sunflower oil)** in the chemical shift range between 0 and 11 ppm. The values above and below the spectrum show the peak positions and peak integration (relative number of protons), respectively.

Figure S7b. ^1H NMR spectrum of **Sample 1 (Pristine sunflower oil)** in the chemical shift range between 3.6 to 5.7 ppm. The values above and below the spectrum show the peak positions and peak integration (relative number of protons), respectively.

Figure S7c. ^1H NMR spectrum of **Sample 1 (Pristine sunflower oil)** in the chemical shift range between 0.45 to 3.1 ppm. The values above and below the spectrum show the peak positions and peak integration (relative number of protons), respectively.

Figure S8a. ^1H NMR spectrum of **Sample 2 (TBAI + sunflower oil)** in the chemical shift range between 0 and 11 ppm. The values above and below the spectrum show the peak positions and peak integration (relative number of protons), respectively.

Figure S8b. ^1H NMR spectrum of **Sample 2 (TBAI + sunflower oil)** in the chemical shift range between 3.7 and 5.8 ppm. The values above and below the spectrum show the peak positions and peak integration (relative number of protons), respectively.

Figure S8c. ^1H NMR spectrum of **Sample 2 (TBAI + sunflower oil)** in the chemical shift range between 1.7 and 3.75 ppm. The values above and below the spectrum show the peak positions and peak integration (relative number of protons), respectively.

Figure S8d. ^1H NMR spectrum of **Sample 2 (TBAI + sunflower oil)** in the chemical shift range between 0.6 and 1.75 ppm. The values above and below the spectrum show the peak positions and peak integration (relative number of protons), respectively.

Figure S9a. ^1H NMR spectrum of **Sample 3 (Sunflower oil treated with NO_2 gas)** in the chemical shift range between 0 and 10.5 ppm. The values above and below the spectrum show the peak positions and peak integration (relative number of protons), respectively.

Figure S9b. ^1H NMR spectrum of **Sample 3 (Sunflower oil treated with NO_2 gas)** in the chemical shift range between 3.8 and 5.9 ppm. The values above and below the spectrum show the peak positions and peak integration (relative number of protons), respectively.

Figure S9c. ^1H NMR spectrum of **Sample 3 (Sunflower oil treated with NO_2 gas)** in the chemical shift range between 0.4 and 2.9 ppm. The values above and below the spectrum show the peak positions and peak integration (relative number of protons), respectively.

Figure S10a. ^1H NMR spectrum of **Sample 4 (TBAI + sunflower oil, treated with NO_2 gas)** in the chemical shift range between 0 and 10.5 ppm. The values above and below the spectrum show the peak positions and peak integration (relative number of protons), respectively.

Figure S10b. ^1H NMR spectrum of **Sample 4 (TBAI + sunflower oil, treated with NO_2 gas)** in the chemical shift range between 3.7 and 5.75 ppm. The values above and below the spectrum show the peak positions and peak integration (relative number of protons), respectively.

Figure S10c. ^1H NMR spectrum of **Sample 4 (TBAI + sunflower oil, treated with NO_2 gas)** in the chemical shift range between 1.6 and 3.4 ppm. The values above and below the spectrum show the peak positions and peak integration (relative number of protons), respectively.

Figure S10d. ^1H NMR spectrum of **Sample 4 (TBAI + sunflower oil, treated with NO_2 gas)** in the chemical shift range between 0.55 and 2.15 ppm. The values above and below the spectrum show the peak positions and peak integration (relative number of protons), respectively.

Figure S12a. ^1H NMR spectrum of **Sample 6 (TBAI treated with NO_2 gas)** in the chemical shift range between 0 and 11 ppm. The values above and below the spectrum show the peak positions and peak integration (relative number of protons), respectively.

Figure S12b. ^1H NMR spectrum of **Sample 6 (TBAI treated with NO_2 gas)** in the chemical shift range between 0.6 and 3.5 ppm. The values above and below the spectrum show the peak positions and peak integration (relative number of protons), respectively.

Table S6. Results from ^1H NMR spectroscopy characterization. All ^1H NMR spectra are presented in Figure S7–S12.

Sample	Intervals of characteristic features / chemical shift positions (ppm)
Pristine sunflower oil (Sample 1)	0.7529–0.7865; 0.8401–0.8659; 1.1593–1.3107; 1.4588–1.5069; 1.8907–1.9897; 2.0037–2.0300; 2.1151–2.1433; 2.2541–2.2824; 2.4967–2.5071; 2.6244–2.6491; 2.7181–2.7297; 3.9555–3.9901; 4.1515–4.1828; 5.1639–5.2402; 5.2946–5.3427.
TBAI + sunflower oil (Sample 2)	0.7533–0.7870; 0.7741–0.8662; 0.9219–0.9513; 1.1598–1.2739; 1.2739–1.3479; 1.4579–1.4949; 1.5373–1.5842; 1.8910–1.9461; 1.9685–2.0167; 2.1157–2.1443; 2.2399–2.2968; 2.4970–2.5040; 2.6250–2.6498; 2.7180–2.7405; 3.1458–3.1794; 3.3101; 3.9567–3.9920; 4.0983–4.1833; 4.2477–4.2778; 5.1644–5.2286; 5.2944–5.3441.
Sunflower oil treated with NO_2 gas (Sample 3)	0.8345–0.8610; 1.1110; 1.2313; 1.4951; 1.9360–1.9904; 2.2556–2.2694; 2.4979–2.5049; 2.6290–2.6789; 4.0989–4.1349; 4.2385–4.2599; 5.1779–5.1832; 5.2557; 5.3148–5.3648.
TBAI + sunflower oil, treated with NO_2 gas (Sample 4)	0.8354–0.8614; 0.9220–0.9514; 1.1661; 1.2321; 1.2831–1.3327; 1.4964; 1.5360–1.5829; 1.9361–2.0148; 2.2556–2.2824; 2.4937–2.5080; 2.6319–2.7389; 3.1447–3.1784; 3.3167; 3.9698–3.9804; 4.0980–4.1347; 4.2456–4.2534; 5.1774–5.1843; 5.2846–5.3641.
Pre-dried TBAI Powder, as a reference material (Sample 5)	0.9241–0.9536; 1.2856–1.3590; 1.5633–1.6259; 3.1918–3.2255; 3.2967.
TBAI treated with NO_2 gas (Sample 6)	0.9204–0.9499; 1.2786–1.3520; 1.5530–1.6157; 3.1719–3.2057; 7.5187.

S2.2 Behavior of tetra-*n*-butylammonium iodide in *tert*-butanol as solvent

The UV-Vis spectra of TBAI with various concentrations and TBAI exposed to NO_2 recorded in *tert*-butanol are presented in **Figure S2** and the samples description is given in **Table S3**. The spectrum of TBAI in *tert*-butanol with the highest concentration ($\sim 135 \mu\text{mol}\cdot\text{dm}^{-3}$ TBAI) shows distinctive absorption only in the UV region (peaking at ~ 227 nm), while the other two pristine TBAI spectra with lower concentrations show additional peaks at 292 and 360 nm. However, in the case of TBAI with medium concentration ($64 \mu\text{mol}\cdot\text{dm}^{-3}$), the absorption in the UV region shows additional peaks at 219 nm and below. In the case of the lowest concentration ($35 \mu\text{mol}\cdot\text{dm}^{-3}$) the absorption maximum is shifted towards lower values (218 nm and below) compared to TBAI with the highest concentration, but the broad peaks remain at the same positions (292 and 360 nm). It is important to note that the absorption is increasing in the case of the peaks at 292 and 360 within descending TBAI concentration. On the other hand, the spectrum of TBAI exposed to NO_2 shows very similar features, in terms of peak positions at 292 and 360 nm, with the spectra of TBAI with medium and low concentration and such behavior is not observable when methanol is used as solvent, as presented in our previous paper,^[2] and showed in **Figure 2b** in the main text of this research, even though the concentrations are not significantly different (81 in **Figure 2b** versus $100 \mu\text{mol}\cdot\text{dm}^{-3}$ in Singh et al.^[2]). The broad features at 292 and 360 nm can be assigned to absorption of triiodide anion (I_3^-),^[2-4] which is possibly in equilibrium with iodide (I^-) and molecular iodine (I_2). The equilibrium is presented with **Equation S3**.

Evidence for this claim are the UV-Vis spectra of elemental iodine and TBAI exposed to NO_2 recorded in methanol, presented in **Figure 2b** in the main text, showing broad peaks with absorption maximum at 290 and 359 nm. The molecular iodine (I_2) is formed by oxidation of the iodide anion (I^-) from TBAI when exposed to humid NO_2 , as discussed in **Subsection 3.2** of the main text. In a consecutive reaction, the as-produced molecular I_2 reacts with excess TBAI thus forming tetra-*n*-butylammonium

triiodide - $(C_4H_9)_4NI_3$ (abbreviated as $TBAI_3$), or in a simpler manner it reacts with iodide (I^-) to form the triiodide ion (I_3^-) anion, presented with **Equation S4** and **Equation S5**, respectively. The reaction mechanism presented with **Equation S4** and **Equation S5** is already discussed in our previous publication^[2] and supported by the spectroscopic findings in this research.

Equation S4

Equation S5

However, the main focus of this subsection will be placed on the chemical behavior of TBAI dissolved in *tert*-butanol. Namely, as previously mentioned above in the text, TBAI in *tert*-butanol at medium and low concentrations show broad peaks at ~290 and ~360 nm (**Figure S2**) typical for the $I_3^-/I^-/I_2$ equilibrium originating from tetra-*n*-butylammonium triiodide – $TBAI_3$ (**Equations S3-S5**), attributed to absorption of the I_3^- anion in our previous publication.^[2] Consequently, the question naturally arises, how the I_3^- anion or elemental I_2 are formed from pristine TBAI when dissolved in *tert*-butanol at medium ($64 \mu\text{mol}\cdot\text{dm}^{-3}$) and low concentrations ($35 \mu\text{mol}\cdot\text{dm}^{-3}$) but not in the case of higher concentration ($\sim 135 \mu\text{mol}\cdot\text{dm}^{-3}$) and also not in the case when this substance is dissolved in methanol?

Unfortunately, there is no clear explanation of the reaction mechanism, yet some experimental and literature results are discussed in the following text. Namely, what is commonly known is that TBAI can dissociate into TBA^+ cation and I^- anion in *tert*-butanol as a protic polar solvent (**Equation S6**).

Equation S6

Then, in a next step, the $I^-(t\text{-butanol})$ somehow undergoes per se oxidation into I_2 , which is in equilibrium with I_3^- . The claim for identification of species like I_2 in equilibrium with I_3^- is undoubtedly correct when the UV-Vis spectra (broad peaks with absorption maximum at 290 and 359 nm) in **Figure S2** are compared with the UV-Vis spectra in **Figure 2b** in the main text and in our previous paper,^[2] as discussed above in this subsection. Additionally, the formation of iodine (I_2) in from TBAI in *tert*-butanol as solvent can be also visually observed from the experimental results presented on **Figure S3**. Namely, for this experiment, 100 mg TBAI are dissolved in 10 mL *tert*-butanol in two separate test tubes from which the first one was kept exposed under sunlight and second one in dark and 100 mg TBAI are dissolved in 10 mL methanol in a third test tube and kept only under sunlight. All three test tubes are closed with septum stopper and left at room temperature. Over the course of few hours the solution in both test tubes with TBAI in *tert*-butanol (kept in light and dark) turned pale yellow and remained unchanged for one week, suggesting that the above-mentioned formation of I_2 does not necessarily follow a photochemical pathway but the $I^-(t\text{-butanol})$ anion originating from the dissociation of TBAI (**Equation S6**) maybe undergoes oxidation caused by dissolved atmospheric oxygen? On the other hand, when methanol is used as solvent for TBAI and the test tube is kept under ambient light there is no observable color change (**Figure S3**), which is supporting the results presented in **Figure 2b** in the main text (no observation of broad peaks at ~290 and ~360 nm – typical for $I_3^-/I^-/I_2$ equilibrium when TBAI is dissolved in methanol). The experiment proceeded by opening all three test tubes and leaving them under air exposure and sunlight for one week. No further color change was observed in all three test tubes that is different from what is presented in **Figure S3**. Finally, air was bubbled for several minutes in all test tubes and again no color change is observed, different than the colors of the solutions presented in **Figure S3**, which is rather unexpected and the presumption that atmospheric oxygen causes the oxidation of I^- anion into molecular I_2 is not very accurate. It appears that the formation of I_2 from TBAI is somehow solvent dependent proposing that *tert*-butanol, as a tertiary alcohol and less polar than methanol, creates conditions for favorable oxidation of the I^- anion into I_2 under both sunlight exposure and dark conditions, but according to our brief experiments, not much affected by the dissolved atmospheric O_2 and maybe affected by some impurities originating from the TBAI synthesis procedure. The exact mechanistic pathways are unclear and to the best of our knowledge the literature sources focusing exactly on this problematic are rather scarce or hardly available. Such reaction

mechanisms are worth being more thoroughly investigated in future research, including experiments under inert conditions, highly purified TBAI, and using various solvents for TBAI and various sources of I⁻ anion.

S3. References

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